

THE IMPORTANCE OF STATE UNITS IN FORMING QUALITY PRESS SERVICE ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In society openness policy good quality and impressive way organize reach in processes the press service state units and their place about

Key words: state unit, press service, departments, openness policy, openness level.

In society management in politics openness provide this population with efficient and strong connections installation means this equal to while there is of problems level becomes clear and necessary has been of solutions importance expected from the degree higher level organize to find take will come.

It's own in place while in society of individuals according to word in freedom activation and management bodies people with communication active to enter take will come.

President's speech " People with communication, people dreams, aspirations, pain and worries with to live state policy level rising today's in the day each one public information tool really communication to the platform, free thought to the pulpit has become only if we own to us put to goals reach " We will get it," ¹he said words at the heart of this obvious example let's see can

This is openness of politics existence people with communication develop can't There is of the system efficient just looks his goals realization ensure take necessary.

In this while worker day and in the field of actions fulfillment processes are also important.

I mean, organization done administration, state institutions and organizations people or purposeful audience with efficient communication for their of existence himself enough does not There is processes about message to give and to the situation relatively acceptance of the doer attitude learning in the process systematic and considerate group performance it is necessary

And this organization and of institutions state units go is worn

¹ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Law priority and human being interests provision - country development and people of well-being pledge // People word , 2016 December 8 .

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- State organs and organizations central in the devices information services employees the number belongs to office of activity to himself characteristic come came out without his leader by is determined
- State organs and organizations departmental and territorial departments information services activities organize reach belongs to of offices out of need come out determination can " ². Here it is that's it from the decision come came out without in places the press service employees the number is defined

For example Bukhara city governorship the press in service Press secretary , operator, operator, press employee activity walking of them only 2 people the press service department state together acceptance done is considered The rest employees while another departments contained employee as the press service activities performs

And this the press service to the activity effect shows . Because the press service employee own in turn salary and imitations in terms of is noteworthy. This is it department in the composition working employee high level work process done if it increases, its to the salary some kind of addition is added. Most considerate side employee this department in the composition activity take if it goes his salary units his from the activity come out high level is determined. Good right while good activity determines

In particular , Uzbekistan Republic Measures of the President of June 27, 2022 to support the mass media and develop the field of journalism about". This is also the decision PQ-294 obvious is evidence .

That's it with together, the state units regarding international attention from the field is big. "PR environment organize in doing the work taking into account the environment get" (Alyoshina).

For example in General Motors this 200 people in the unit works 100 of them expert and the remaining 100 helper employee is counted. Of course, General Motors its income is US \$228.037 billion. Workers the number and December 2019 month to the situation according to 164,000 people to PR this level attention giving company of the product quality according to high in place stands Such the result while public with contact to the basis built is considered That is PR department in the company active respectively of the population to the product has been attitude learn them improved the product presentation is enough That's it with together the audience persuasion in order to reliable information service to the road sheep ok.

² Uzbekistan Republic President Sh. MIRZIYOYEV, Tashkent city, June 27, 2019, PQ-4366
Uzbekistan Republic Decision of the President No. PQ-4366 dated June 27, 2019

This the situation Russia of the Federation Primorsky country Press service as we can see in the example can Field in terms of 164 673 km³ which ranks 23rd in the country population of in terms of and with 11.9 people /km² which ranks 25th in the country of the area Press 4 people in service activity take goes³ Theirs one lawyer to be, of the department legal issues with is engaged. The rest while of the department specialists as activity take they go.

Summary by doing to say. As for the press service employees state in units department in the composition activity conduct department efficiency and direction the future for work will give. Because, the organization or institution the press service activities take going the employee is the head of the country and the country by being given out of consideration use if possible, and from him his own in consideration if he feels that directly he work coefficient all of them that's it looks Both his own successors family for profitable and considerate occupation has been this to the field directs. And this own in turn in the future employees selective in boa opportunity increases and competition surface cause the most good quality personnel Create for the ground creates

I own article through the press service of the department state units the number increase offer I will tell you .

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Law priority and human being interests provision - development of the country and people of well-being pledge // People word , 2016 December 8
2. Uzbekistan Republic President Sh. Mirziyoyev , Tashkent city, June 27, 2019, decision PQ- 4366 Uzbekistan Republic No. PF-5618. 09.01.2019 .
3. Lex.uz website .
4. Rabota press secretary i press- slujby administration the subject
5. Rossiyskoy Federation , Nikolayev A.Yu. , Geraskin SV, Borisov IV, Kretinin A.Ye ., Sysoyev KA Novosibirsk 1997

³ Rabota press secretary i press- slujb y administration subject Rossiyskoy Federation , Nikolayev A.Yu. , Geraskin SV, Borisov IV, Kretinin A. Ye ., S y soyev KA Novosibirsk 1997